

THE BENEFITS OF ENGLISH AS A MEDIUM OF INSTRUCTION FOR SAUDI DIPLOMA STUDENTS - A CASE STUDY OF UGLAT ASUGOUR APPLIED COLLEGE BRANCH

BY

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to show the benefits of using English language as a medium of teaching Saudi diploma students. The study sample consisted of 30 diploma students taken randomly from Applied College, Uglat Asugour Branch, Qassim University during the second semester in the academic year 2025-2026 and 15 instructors from Qassim University Colleges. The researcher used interviews for diploma students and a questionnaire for instructors. The results of the study indicated that:

- 1. Students showed important improvement in English language skills, especially in vocabulary, reading, and listening.*
- 2. Learning through English increased students' motivation and engagement in their studies.*
- 3. Learning through English allowed students to use modern textbooks, online materials, and international scientific resources without translation barriers.*
- 4. Students felt more prepared for the job market, with English skills seen as a key advantage by employers.*
- 5. Some students struggled with English at the start, and instructors highlighted the need for better support and training.*

Due to the above results, the study Recommends the following:

- 1. Establish preparatory courses and regular language workshops to help students overcome initial difficulties.*
- 2. Offer professional development programs focused on teaching technical subjects through English.*
- 3. Develop glossaries and materials that combine Arabic and English to assist students in early stages.*
- 4. Introduce English instruction over time to allow students time to adapt.*
- 5. Collect feedback regularly to improve teaching strategies and address student needs.*
- 6. Encourage students to practice English through clubs, presentations, and training programs.*

مستخلص البحث

هدفت هذه الدراسة الي التعرف علي فوائد استخدام اللغة الانجليزية كلغة للتدريس لطلاب الدبلوم السعوديين. تكونت عينة الدراسة من 30 طالب دبلوم تم اختيارهم عشوائيا من الكلية التطبيقية - فرع عقلة الصقور بجامعة القصيم خلال الفصل الدراسي الثاني للعام 2025- 2026 و 15 أستاذ من كليات جامعة القصيم . استخدم الباحث المقابلات و الاستبيان للطلاب و المحاضرين وقد أظهرت نتائج الدراسة ما يلي:

- 1- أظهر الطلاب تحسناً ملحوظاً في مهارات اللغة الإنجليزية، خاصة في المفردات، والقراءة، والاستماع
- 2- أدى التعلم باللغة الإنجليزية إلى زيادة دافعية الطلاب ومشاركتهم في الدراسة
- 3- مكّنهم التعلم باللغة الإنجليزية من استخدام الكتب الدراسية الحديثة، والمواد الإلكترونية، والمصادر العلمية العالمية دون عوائق الترجمة
- 4- شعر الطلاب بأنهم أكثر استعداداً لسوق العمل، حيث تُعد مهارات اللغة الإنجليزية ميزة رئيسية لدى أصحاب العمل-
- 5- واجه بعض الطلاب صعوبات في اللغة الإنجليزية في البداية، وأشار الأساتذة إلى ضرورة توفير دعم وتدريب أفضل وبناءً على النتائج السابقة، توصي الدراسة بما يلي:
 - 1 إنشاء دورات تمهيدية وورش عمل لغوية مستمرة لمساعدة الطلاب على تجاوز الصعوبات الأولية
 - 2 تقديم برامج تطوير مهني تركز على تعليم المواد التقنية باللغة الإنجليزية
 - 3 إعداد مصطلحات و مواد تعليمية تجمع بين اللغتين العربية والإنجليزية لمساعدة الطلاب في المراحل المبكرة
 - 4 إدخال التعليم باللغة الإنجليزية تدريجياً لإعطاء الطلاب الوقت الكافي للتأقلم
 - 5 جمع الملاحظات والتغذية الراجعة بانتظام لتحسين استراتيجيات التدريس وتلبية احتياجات الطلاب
 - 6 تشجيع الطلاب على ممارسة اللغة الإنجليزية من خلال الأنشطة، والعروض التقديمية، والبرامج التدريبية

Key word: Benefits, Saudi, Diploma, English, Student

INTRODUCTION

In today's globalized world, English has become a critical language for education, business, and technology. In Saudi Arabia, English proficiency is increasingly important, particularly for students enrolled in diploma programs. These programs often focus on technical and vocational skills that require access to international resources, many of which are available primarily in English (Al-Qahhtani, 2021).

It is noticed that teaching diploma students through English has emerged as a strategic approach to improve both their academic outcomes and future employability.

The use of English as a medium of instruction in non-English-speaking countries has been widely studied across various educational contexts. Scholars agree that English as a medium of instruction

enhances students' academic and professional prospects, particularly in countries undergoing economic modernization, such as Saudi Arabia.

Global Perspectives on English medium instruction:

According to Dearden (2014), the global trend toward English as a medium instruction in higher education reflects the increasing importance of English in the global economy. Researchers such as Coleman (2006) argue that English-medium instruction fosters access to international academic resources and promotes the mobility of students and faculty. These advantages are particularly relevant in technical and vocational education, where the latest research and innovations are often published in English.

English as a Medium of Instruction has been increasingly adopted in Saudi universities to enhance students' global competitiveness and employability. A study by Imam (2020) found that professors and students generally preferred English medium instruction, citing its role in increasing international opportunities and improving graduates' employability. However, the study also highlighted challenges such as varying levels of prior knowledge.

As such, Saudi Arabia has taken significant steps to modernize its education system in line with Vision 2030, which aims to prepare a globally competitive workforce. One of the key changes is the increasing use of English as a medium of instruction in higher education and diploma programs as English language is now widely believed to be a gateway to international knowledge, better job opportunities, and access to scientific and technical resources. Thus, many diploma programs in Saudi Arabia have adopted English as a medium of instruction to enhance students' skills and improve their readiness for labor market.

This study aims to explore the actual advantages that Saudi diploma students gain from learning through English. It also considers how English as a medium of instruction affects their language skills, motivation, access to resources, and employability, based on feedback from students and instructors involved in such programs.

Problems of the Study

Despite the increasing use of English as a Medium of Instruction in Saudi diploma

programs, several problems appear. Many students enter these programs with limited English proficiency, which can hinder their understanding and academic progress. Additionally, not all instructors are fully prepared to teach technical subjects in English, affecting the quality of their teaching. There is also a lack of adequate bilingual resources and support services to help students overcome language barriers. Furthermore, some students experience anxiety and low motivation when studying in English, which impacts on their performance. Thus, assessing students accurately can be challenging due to language difficulties, raising questions about whether English- Medium Instruction truly enhances academic outcomes and employability or if it creates additional obstacles.

Hypotheses of the Study:

This study investigated the following Hypotheses:

1. Teaching Saudi diploma students through English improves their English language proficiency.
2. Teaching Saudi diploma students through English increases their motivation and engagement in their studies.
3. Saudi diploma students who were taught through English have better access to up-to-date academic resources compared to those taught in Arabic.
4. Teaching Saudi diploma students through English enhances students' employability and readiness for the global job market.

5. There are challenges related to language barriers that affect some students' academic performance in English Medium Instruction programs.

instructors, in order to enhance future support programs to address language barriers. Overall, the study supports Saudi Arabia's vision to advance education quality and workforce readiness through effective English instruction.

Questions of the Study:

Therefore, the study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the advantages of teaching diploma-level students in Saudi Arabia through English?
2. How does English as a Medium of Instruction affect students' English language development?
3. In what ways does Medium Instruction impact students' academic performance and motivation?
4. How does Medium Instruction influence students' employment opportunities and future career paths?
5. What challenges are faced by students and instructors in Medium Instruction programs?

The Significance of the Study:

This study is important because it emphasized the benefits of using English as a medium of instruction for Saudi diploma students. These benefits can help educators and policymakers improve teaching methods and prepare students for local and international job markets. The findings of this study also highlight the role of English proficiency in enhancing students' academic performance and motivation. This study also identified challenges faced by students and

English as a Medium of Instruction in the Middle East and Saudi Arabia

In the Gulf region, English has become a key component of educational reform. A study by Al-Issa (2017) highlights that Gulf countries, including Saudi Arabia, are increasingly using English in higher education to align with global standards and labor market needs. In Saudi Arabia specifically, Barnawi and Al-Hazmi (2016) noted that English is viewed as a tool for economic growth and modernization, especially in technical and vocational institutions.

Benefits for Diploma Students

Several studies focus on the benefits of English as a medium of instruction for students in technical and diploma programs. For instance, Khan (2011) found that Saudi students in English-taught diploma programs showed improved confidence, employability, and academic performance. Similarly, Al-Seghayer (2013) pointed out that using English in vocational training enhances students' ability to engage with technical content and increases their competitiveness in both local and international job markets.

Challenges in English-medium instruction Implementation

Despite its benefits, English-medium instruction presents challenges such as student resistance, limited English proficiency, and insufficient pedagogical support. According to Rabab'ah and Al-Matrafi (2021), these issues can hinder learning if not properly addressed. The literature suggests the importance of balancing English instruction with adequate language support and culturally relevant teaching practices.

In English as a medium of instruction settings, students often encounter significant challenges. A case study of Shousha (2021) revealed that Saudi diploma students at King Abdulaziz University struggled with listening, speaking, and reading comprehension, particularly in higher cognitive skills like inferring meaning from context. These difficulties were contributed to institutional, academic, and pedagogical barriers, including limited exposure to English and gaps in their previous education.

In order to reduce the challenges of English as a medium of instruction, instructors employ various strategies. Alanzi and Curle (2025) found that teachers in Saudi Arabian medical education settings used techniques such as simplifying language, integrating students' first language selectively, and employing repetition and examples to facilitate understanding. These strategies, along with effective classroom management, helped improve student engagement and comprehension in linguistically diverse environments.

To enhance the effectiveness of English as a medium of instruction, several

recommendations have been proposed. Imam (2020) suggested the inclusion of ESP instruction in the curriculum and the development of additional tools and resources to support teacher development. Similarly, Altheyab and Alalwi (2023) recommended careful institutional planning and support to address the challenges associated with English as a medium of instruction in the transition year.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a qualitative research approach to explore the perceived advantages of teaching Saudi diploma students through English. The methodology was designed to gather insights from students and instructors who were selected randomly from diploma colleges in Saudi Arabia.

Research Design

A case study design was employed to provide an in-depth understanding of how English as a medium of instruction affects students in real educational settings. This approach allowed for a detailed examination of both benefits and contextual challenges.

Study Population

The study involved 30 diploma students from Applied College, Uglat Asugour Branch, Qassim University, Saudi Arabia and 15 instructors who teach diploma-level subjects in English from different colleges in Qassim University. The sample of the study were taken randomly.

Data Collection Methods

Two main tools were used:

- **Instructors' Questionnaire:**

A questionnaire was designed to diploma-level teachers of English to collect data on their perceptions, experience, and practices related to teaching Saudi students through English. The questionnaire covers perceived benefits, challenges, and suggested improvements regarding English-medium instruction in teaching.

The questionnaire is divided into two sections. The first part deals with background information and the second one deals with perceptions of English medium instruction to assess teachers' views on the effectiveness of teaching through English in improving student outcomes, enhancing employability, and accessing global content. This section focused on instructor's opinions and experiences regarding teaching through English language. It included Likert-scale (e.g., Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree), in terms of multiple-choice questions to address the themes: the benefits of English medium instruction, the impact on students' employability, challenges faced by instructors and students, instructional strategies used to support students and finally the recommendation

The researcher conducted interview with 30 Saudi diploma students about the benefits of being taught through English. To ensure the validity, the researcher consulted subject-matter experts of teaching English as a second or foreign language and academic staff experts to see if the questions are relevant and complete.

Data Analysis

The data collected through interviews and focus groups were analyzed with revealed

several recurring themes regarding the advantages of English-medium instruction in Saudi diploma programs. The analysis focused on participants' perceptions, supported by direct quotes and cross-comparisons between student and instructor responses.

FINDINGS AND INTERPRETATIONS

Finding from this study revealed the following:

❖ Students' Interview:

Students' Response to the Interview:

In order to answer the research questions, the following showed the response of the students to the interview

- **Improved language skills**

Many students indicated that learning through English helps improve their English proficiency, especially speaking, listening, reading, and writing.

“At first, it was hard, but now I understand technical words more easily. I can even read manuals and research online without translating everything.” – Diploma Student

This finding matches with Al-Shehri, A. S. (2019) who observed that English medium instruction contributes to greater language fluency among Saudi students in technical education.

- **Better Career Opportunities**

All the participants agree that English is an international language, this leads to better jobs prospects both locally and internationally. Students and instructors agreed that English medium instruction

made graduates more attractive to employers, especially in fields like IT, engineering, and healthcare. This supports the findings of (Barnawi & Al-Hazmi, 2016), which identifies English as essential for competitiveness in the Saudi and international job market.

- **Access to Global Knowledge and Resources**

Teaching in English allows diploma students to access a wide range of educational sources, research paper, and technology that are available in English. All the participants appreciated being able to access international textbooks, online tutorials, and scientific journals.

“We can watch YouTube lectures and read research papers. Everything is in English, and now we understand it.” – Diploma student.

- **Enhance Communication:**

The majority of the participants indicated that learning in English helps them communicate effectively with people from different countries, which is important in many professional fields.

- **Increased Confidence and Academic Motivation**

All the subjects noted that learning in English made them feel more capable and

globally connected, encouraging them to achieve further education or international certifications.

“I want to study abroad after my diploma. English helps me think it’s possible.” – Diploma Student. This reflects the argument made by Al-Seghayer (2013) that English medium instruction boosts student ambition and self-confidence.

Challenges Noted

While the overall perception of English - medium instruction was positive, some challenges were acknowledged such as Initial language barriers, Instructor preparedness, and uneven student proficiency levels. However, students suggested that bilingual support, vocabulary lists, and English workshops helped mitigate these issues over time. Instructors also recommended professional development in EMI strategies.

- ❖ **Instructors’ Response to the Questionnaire:**

The responses of instructors to the questionnaire on teaching Saudi diploma students through English revealed many themes. Instructors’ responses reflect both pedagogical insights and practical challenges drawn from their classroom experiences.

Table 1: Perceived Benefits of Teaching Through English

Item	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	SD
Teaching through English improves students' language proficiency	60%	30%	7%	3%	0%	4.47	0.79
English instruction enhances students' job readiness	67%	27%	3%	3%	0%	4.57	0.74
English enhances critical and communication skills	53%)	33%	10%	3%	0%	4.37	0.83
Students become more confident when using English in academic settings	50%	33%	10%	7%	0%	4.27	0.89

As it can be seen in the above table, a majority of instructors agreed that teaching in English positively impacts students. 90% of instructors (60% strongly agree, 30% agree) reported that students' English proficiency improved, indicating that English-medium instruction enhances language acquisition. 94% believed it enhances employability, aligning with global

workplace demands. 86% agreed that English as a medium of instruction develops critical thinking and communication skills, and 83% reported an increase in student confidence in using English. These findings suggest that instructors strongly support the integration of English in diploma programs for both academic and career development.

Table 2: Challenges Instructors Face When Using English Medium Instruction

Item	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	SD
Students find it difficult to understand lessons in English	40%	33%	17%	7%	3%	3.97	1.02
Lack of English-medium instruction teaching materials resources	47%	30%	17%	7%	0%	4.17	0.93
Instructors need more English medium instruction - specific training	73%	20%	3%	3%	0%	4.63	0.72
Students are more passive in English-taught classes	33%	37%	20%	10%	0%	3.93	0.98

The above table shows the challenges that instructors face as they use English -medium instruction. Here, instructors identified significant challenges: 73% of instructors agreed that students struggle to understand English-taught lessons, and 77% noted a lack of suitable English medium instruction materials. A substantial 93% of instructors

felt there is a need for more English medium instruction training, highlighting a gap in professional development. 70% agreed that students tend to be more passive in English medium instruction settings, possibly due to lack of confidence or low language proficiency.

Table 3: Strategies Used to Support Students

Item	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	mean	S/D
Use of visual aids and real-life examples to explain complex topics	57%	33%	17%	7%	3%	4.20	0.91
Code- switching (Arabic- English) helps bridge understanding	63%	23%	17%	7%	0%	4.30	0.86

Group work and peer interaction improve English use	60%	30%	7%	3%	0%	4.47	0.73
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Table (3) revealed the main strategies that can be used to support students. Instructors reported using several adaptive strategies: 90% use visuals and real-life examples to clarify complex ideas. 86% apply code-switching (Arabic-English) to help students grasp difficult content. 90% promote group

work and peer interaction to create a collaborative and less intimidating English-speaking environment. These showed that instructors employ flexible and culturally sensitive approaches to support student comprehension and engagement in English medium instruction contexts.

Table 4: Suggestion for Improving English -medium instruction

Item	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	S/D
Providing more teacher training programs in English medium instruction	70%	27%	3%	7%	0%	4.53	0.67
Developing bilingual support materials (English-Arabic)	67%	27%	3%	3%	0%	4.57	0.66
Encouraging English conversation clubs or extra-curriculars	60%	33%	3%	3%	0%	4.50	0.68

As it can be seen in table (4), instructors made clear recommendations for improving English medium instruction in Saudi diploma institutions: 97% supported more teacher training programs focused on EMI methods. 94% endorsed the development of bilingual (English-Arabic) materials. 93% recommended encouraging English conversation clubs and other activities to enhance speaking skills outside the classroom. This indicates that there is strong consensus that the success of English as a medium of instruction depends not only on

teaching practices but also on institutional support, curriculum development, and extracurricular engagement.

The above results revealed that instructors see clear academic, linguistic, and professional benefits to teaching through English. However, they also emphasize the need for targeted support, particularly in the form of training, resources, and language development strategies. The combination of high perceived value and clear instructional challenges reflects a critical need for a

structured English- medium instruction framework in Saudi diploma education.

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to explore the benefits of teaching Saudi diploma students through English. The literature consistently shows that English-medium instruction improves students' language proficiency, enabling them to access a wider range of academic and technical materials. Additionally, English-medium instruction enhances academic performance by fostering critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Importantly, English proficiency increases employability prospects, as many employers in Saudi Arabia prefer candidates with strong English skills. However, challenges such as language barriers and the need for teacher training were also highlighted.

This study therefore explored the perception of both Saudi diploma students and their instructors regarding the use of English as a medium of instruction. The findings reveal a general agreement on the potential academic and professional benefits of English as a medium of instruction, as well as the challenges that accompany its implementation in diploma- level education.

From the perspective of the diploma students, most of them expressed a positive attitude towards being taught in English. they believed that that English as a medium instruction helps them improve their language skills, especially in vocabulary

listening, and speaking. Many students felt that learning in English would enhance their job opportunities, particularly in technical and business-related fields where English is commonly used. However, a significant number of students also reported that they sometimes struggle to understand lessons entirely delivered in English. this was especially true for students with a weak foundation in the language. As a result, some students felt less confident in participating in classrooms discussions or completing assignments, especially in more complex subjects.

Despite these challenges, students appreciated supportive strategies such as the use of visual aids, group work, and simplified explanations. Many suggested the need for extra language support, such as English- speaking clubs or additional English preparation courses.

Instructors largely supported English as a medium of instruction, emphasizing its role in developing students' language proficiency, critical thinking, and global competitiveness. They believed that students who are taught in English are better prepared for both the workplace and higher education. A large majority observed that students become more confident and independent over time when exposed to English in an academic context.

In addition to that, instructors pointed out several challenges. They noted that students lacked the English skills needed to fully grasp course content. This sometimes slowed down the teaching process and required instructors to approach teaching more programmatically. Furthermore, instructors highlighted the lack of English as a medium of instruction training and limited bilingual teaching resources as barriers to effect instruction. To address these challenges, instructors used a variety of strategies, including code-switching, scaffolding, and per -based activities. They also recommended the need for structured training programs for teachers and the creation of more bilingual materials to support content delivery.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study indicate that both Saudi diploma students and their instructors generally view English -medium instruction as beneficial for academic and professional development. English- medium instruction was found to enhance students' language proficiency, boost their confidence, and prepare them for global job markets. Instructors also acknowledge its role in developing critical thinking and communication skills

Teaching Saudi diploma students through English offers significant advantages in language development, academic success, and employability. While challenges remain, such as ensuring adequate language support and teacher preparedness, the benefits far outweigh these obstacles. English-medium instruction aligns well with Saudi Arabia's broader educational and economic goals of

preparing a skilled, globally competitive workforce.

To maximize the benefits of English-medium instruction for Saudi diploma students, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Implement comprehensive English language support programs to help students overcome initial language difficulties.
2. Provide specialized training for teachers to improve their English proficiency and instructional methods in EMI settings.
3. Integrate practical and contextualized English materials relevant to students' fields of study to increase engagement and comprehension.
4. Encourage continuous assessment and feedback to monitor student progress and adapt teaching strategies accordingly.

DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY

This study is limited to Saudi diploma students of Applied Colleges (students of Uglat Asugour Branch as a sample) during the academic year (2025-2026). The generalization will be limited to this population and to instruments used in this study.

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